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THE PUTATIVE PTEROSAUR TRACKS AT GUNSTON HALL (POTOMAC GROUP, CRETACEOUS OF VIRGINIA) ARE EXAMPLES OF EROSION

Skye N. McDavid^{1,2,*} and Henry N. Thomas³

¹Lauer Foundation for Paleontology, Science, and Education, 1421 S Gables Blvd, Wheaton, Illinois 60189
mail@skymcdavid.com <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2529-1812>

²Delaware Valley Paleontological Society, PO Box 686, Plymouth Meeting, Pennsylvania 19462;

³Idaho State University, 921 S 8th Ave, Pocatello, Idaho 83209; henrythomas@isu.edu <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-6189-2060>

*corresponding author

ABSTRACT - Putative pterosaur tracks have recently been reported from the Potomac Group of Virginia, integrated into the cornerstones of Gunston Hall near Lorton in Fairfax County. These putative pterosaur tracks are reexamined. They bear little resemblance to known pterosaur tracks, including those known from other Potomac Group localities. However, they are consistent with examples of erosion seen on other sandstone blocks at Gunston Hall and elsewhere and are interpreted as examples of erosion and breakage from chiseling. This highlights the importance of demonstrating a biological origin of putative ichnofossils in malleable sediments.

Keywords: Pterosauria, Ichnology, *Pteraichnus*, Potomac Group, Virginia

INTRODUCTION

Pterosaurs had hands and feet (Wellnhofer 1978), and the imprints of these are not infrequently preserved in the fossil record (Lockley et al. 1995; 2008). Pterosaur manus and pes tracks have been reported across the globe, primarily in Late Jurassic and Cretaceous sediments (Barrett et al. 2008; Lockley et al. 2008). These ichnofossils have provided evidence for aspects of pterosaur behavior and ecology, including foraging behavior (e.g. Lockley and Wright 2003). Pterosaur ichnotaxonomy is controversial, however; only a single ichnogenus, *Pteraichnus*, is widely recognized as being

pterosaurian in origin. Other putative pterosaur ichnotaxa are disputed, with alternate interpretations suggesting that these represent pseudosuchian, lepidosauromorph, mammal, or limulid tracks (e.g. Lockley et al. 2008; Sánchez-Hernández et al. 2009; Wroblewski 2023).

The Potomac Group, encompassing the Raritan, Patapsco, Arundel, and Patuxent Formations is exposed in Maryland, Virginia, and the District of Columbia (Fig. 1). In particular, the Patuxent Formation is an ichnofossiliferous unit dating to the Aptian Stage of the Early Cretaceous Period

(Stanford et al. 2007; 2018). *Pteraichnus* and *Pteraichnus*-like tracks have been reported from the Patuxent Formation in Maryland (Kranz 1998;

Stanford et al. 2007; 2018), including on the grounds of the NASA Goddard Space Flight Center (GSFC) in Greenbelt (Stanford et al. 2018).

Figure 1: Stratigraphy and exposure of the Potomac Group. A: Chart demonstrating the approximate dating of formations and pollen zones of the Potomac Group; based on Jud and Sohn (2016) and Miller et al. (2017). B: Map of Maryland, Virginia, and Washington D.C., with exposure of the Potomac Group highlighted. Locations: 1, Aquia Creek quarry; 2, Gunston Hall; 3, Goddard Space Flight Center. Scale bar equals 20 km. Base map modified from OpenStreetMap available under Open Database License; exposure data modified from Jud and Sohn (2016).

Recently, Weems and Bachman (2023) reported the presence of pterosaur tracks in the cornerstones at Gunston Hall (Fig. 2) near Lorton in Fairfax County, Virginia, which they assigned to the ichnogenus *Pteraichnus*. Gunston Hall is the house of 18th century slaveholder George Mason, now preserved as a historical museum (Kimball 1954, Broadwater 2009). The cornerstones of Gunston Hall were constructed from “Aquia freestone”, sandstone sourced from a quarry along Aquia Creek in Fairfax County. Sandstone from this quarry has been incorporated into many historic structures in Virginia and Washington DC, including the U.S. Capitol Building and the White House (Key et al.

2020). Although considered by Weems and Bachman (2015; 2023) as originating from the Aptian Patuxent Formation, analysis of Aquia sandstone QFR (% quartz: % feldspar: % rock fragments) is more consistent with the younger Patapsco Formation (Key et al. 2020), which is dated to the mid-Albion-Cenomanian stages based on palynostratigraphy (Hochuli et al. 2006; Miller et al. 2017). Here we revisit the putative pterosaur ichnofossils of Gunston Hall and reassess whether these markings are truly pterosaurian or non-biological in origin.

Figure 2: Gunston Hall, as preserved in November 2024. See Kimball (1954) for history of the building. Photo by S. McDavid.

METHODS

The putative Gunston Hall tracks were reexamined in person by the authors and photographed. These were compared to better-preserved pterosaur tracks, particularly those reported from elsewhere in the Potomac Group (see Stanford et al. 2007; 2018). Angle measurements of genuine and putative pterosaur tracks were taken using ImageJ (Abràmoff et al. 2004) from original photographs in the case of Gunston Hall and published photographs for other specimens. All were measured from the distal tips of digit I and III impressions, with the medial-most point of the track taken as the vertex.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The putative manus impression (Fig. 3) (erroneously described as a “wing-finger” print in the abstract and “wing toes” in the text) figured in Weems and Bachman (2023: fig. 3A-B) only superficially resembles a pterosaur manus imprint. The

impressions are mostly ill-defined and irregular in outline, in contrast with actual pterosaur manus tracks (e.g., Lockley et al. 1995; 2008; Stanford et al. 2018). The putative impressions of digits I and III form an angle of 227° , whereas in actual pterosaur manus tracks, digits I and III form a slightly obtuse angle (101° in the *Pteraidchnus* type specimen, photo from Stokes 1957; 108° in GSFC VP1 (Earth Sciences Collection of NASA Goddard Space Flight Center, Greenbelt, Maryland), photo from Stanford et al. 2018). Furthermore, the putative digit III impression has an unnaturally straight break along the putative posterior edge perpendicular to the long axis of the putative digit III, consistent with breakage from chiseling, but inconsistent with the pointed claws seen in pterosaurs (e.g. Wellnhofer 1978). Furthermore, our reexamination identified additional markings in this block of sandstone and other Gunston Hall blocks that do not show any identifiable ichnofossils, but do exhibit similar marks caused by erosion and/or chiseling.

Figure 3: The putative pterosaur left manus track on Gunston Hall. A, photograph; B, photograph overlain with line drawing highlighting the impressions identified as forming the track by Weems and Bachman (2023). Photo by S. McDavid.

Figure 4: The putative pterosaur pedal track on Gunston Hall. A) photograph; B) photograph overlain with line drawing highlighting the impressions identified as forming the track by Weems and Bachman (2023). Scale is 10 cm with 1 cm increments. Photo by S. McDavid.

Figure 5: Example of *Pteraichnus* from the Patuxent Formation GSFC VP1. A, photograph of manus track; A' photograph of manus track overlain with interpretive line drawing; B, photograph of pes track; B' photograph of pes track overlain with interpretive line drawing. Scale bar is 10 cm. Photographs modified from Stanford et al. 2018. Fig.5, available under a CC-BY 4.0 license, available at <http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>

The putative pedal track (Fig. 4) shows no impression of the sole of the foot, claws, or any other features of a pterosaurian pes (see e.g. Wellnhofer 1978). The putative toes are best described as simple indentations in the rock, all of which are irregularly and inconsistently shaped. No sign of the tarsal or metatarsal regions of the foot is preserved, despite their weight-bearing role for a

pterosaur (Bennett 1997) and expectation of making an impression in sediment. The alleged toes are also located within an eroded area in the sandstone block, and the edges of the putative imprints show no difference from the edges of this erosion. We consider this mark to represent an extension of the erosion in this block.

We observed numerous other examples of indentations in sandstone blocks along the Gunston Hall cornerstones (Fig. 6). These other examples lack any diagnosable pterosaur manual or pedal morphology and are all consistent with erosion and/or chiseling. These additional marks show little morphological difference from the putative ichnofossils and demonstrate unambiguously that the Gunston Hall sandstone displays significant weathering. Matrix that is exposed in a way that leaves it vulnerable to erosion, such as on the corner of a building, is liable to develop markings that may

be confused for ichnofossils. The Aquia “freestone” is particularly prone to this, as its composition leaves it vulnerable to weathering when exposed to the elements. This has been noted as early as the 1800s and is a factor that contributed to abandonment of the Aquia Creek quarry after 1840 (Key et al. 2020). In such instances, it is imperative to demonstrate that any putative ichnofossils were impressed when the sediment was deposited and not after exposure. Weems and Bachman (2023) neglected to do so, providing no justification for interpretation of the marks as ichnofossils, let alone pterosaurian ones.

Figure 6: Other examples of erosion and chiseling in the Gunston Hall sandstone. Photos by S. McDavid.

CONCLUSION

The sandstone cornerstones at Gunston Hall do not preserve pterosaur tracks and instead display erosion as would be expected in Aquia sandstone exposed to Virginia weather for over two centuries. The lack of ichnofossils in the Gunston Hall

sandstone is congruent with the lack of reported trackways, pterosaurian or otherwise, from the Patapsco Formation. This highlights the importance of demonstrating biological origins of putative isolated tracks, such as via careful identification of morphological features of the pes and/or manus and

demonstrable differences between non-organic marks in the matrix. We implore field paleontologists to carefully confirm field identifications of ichnofossils prior to publication.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST STATEMENT

Skye N. McDavid is a volunteer social media manager for The Mosasaur/DVPS.

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